

Supplementary Figures S1-S4

Vertical bars report the 95% confidence limits of the coefficients of communality presented in Table 3. These estimates were obtained as accelerated bootstrap confidence intervals produced over 1,000 iterations (Nimon and Oswald, 2013). In each figure, the behaviour considered is indicated in the top (Reading, Spelling, Calculation), and the top graph refers to data for the model based on specific predictors, i.e. Reading predicted by Reading predictors, Spelling predicted by Spelling predictors, and Calculation predicted by Calculation predictors (Zoccolotti et al., 2020). The middle and the bottom graphs refer to data obtained testing the cross-over predictors efficacy. For example: Figure S1 middle graph reports coefficients of communality for Reading predicted by predictors in the Spelling model, and Figure S1 bottom graph reports coefficients of communality for Reading predicted by predictors in the Calculation model.

READING

Specific predictors in the Reading fluency model

Cross-over predictors (predictors in the Spelling model)

Cross-over predictors (predictors in the Calculation model)

Figure S1

SPELLING

Specific predictors in the Spelling model

Cross-over predictors (predictors in the Reading fluency model)

Cross-over predictors (predictors in the Calculation model)

Figure S2

CALCULATION (speed)

Specific predictors in the Calculation model

Cross-over predictors (predictors in the Reading fluency model)

Cross-over predictors (predictors in the Spelling model)

Figure S3

CALCULATION (accuracy)

Specific predictors in the Calculation model

Cross-over predictors (predictors in the Reading fluency model)

Cross-over predictors (predictors in the Spelling model)

Figure S4